

IPBES values assessment

Literature review for the philosophies of good living

Rules for coding relevant records

Information about the document

1. Title of the document
2. Type of document (empirical, review, perspective)
3. Authors of the document or publication (if applicable)
4. Year
5. Summary or abstract of the contribution or article (if applicable)
6. Language in which the document is presented
7. Geographical location - official country
8. Specific information on the location (ej. village or community, protected area, reserve, ejido)

Relation to ILK values

9. Name of the cultural groups/ Indigenous groups/ Local communities
10. Associated values and principles (how they appear explicitly)
11. Types of values according to the typology: instrumental, intrinsic, relational
12. Qualitative description/explanation of the types of values (previous column)
13. Associated key expressions comparable to Good Living (e.g. Sumak Kawsay)
14. Explanation or description on synergies with the "Good Living" philosophy

What messages strongly support evidence to different ILK related topics?¹ Rank from 3 (strongest) to 0 (not related at all).

15. TOPIC 1: On human-nature relationships, biocultural diversity and worldviews
16. TOPIC 2: languages
17. TOPIC 3: On diversity of knowledge for decision-making, including valuation methods
18. TOPIC 4: On self-determination, juridical pluralism, IPLC's rights and institutions and knowledge for decision-making
19. TOPIC 5: On protecting land, territories and places (it could also refer to special cultural places, sacred places, heritage)

¹ The ILK liaison group identified a series of topics present in the first order draft of the chapters and the feedback obtained in the first external review (including the two ILK dialogues organised for the values assessment). Experts participating in this review considered necessary to identify any evidence informing those topics.

20. TOPIC 6: On capacity development (moving forward, looking for solutions)
21. TOPIC 7: On formal and informal education
22. Excerpts about topics

Power

23. Is power mentioned explicitly or implicitly in the document?
24. Excerpts on power; pay special attention to any mentions regarding how power influences decision-making (leave blank if it is not mentioned; repeat if needed from what is mentioned in TOPIC 3)